

Integrating Geosystem Services classifications: a preliminary framework from the piedmont area of the Sesia Val Grande UNESCO Global Geopark

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Abstract— A variety of geological structures, landforms and processes, known as “geodiversity”, influences both human society and natural ecosystems. It offers essential services and benefit as Geosystem Services (GS), a concept raised in the last two decades from the better known “Ecosystem Services” (ES). Despite the importance of GS, their classification remains underdeveloped. The present study integrates the two most accepted classification frameworks for ES and GS, to provide an advanced tool for assessing georesources and planning related management in the piedmont sector of the Sesia Val Grande UNESCO Global Geopark, an area rich in geodiversity and potential GS. By combining literature knowledge, remote sensing and field surveys data in a GIS-based environment, main GS services connected to geological and human activities have been mapped. Results suggest that an integrate classification approach provide a more comprehensive overview of GS in the territory. This in turn is fundamental for achieving more conscious management plans in the perspective of sustainable development within Geopark territories.

I. INTRODUCTION

The Earth we observe today is the product of intricate interactions between long-term geological processes and short-term dynamic processes [1]. The result of these complex interactions is a variety of rocks, minerals, geological structures, landforms and processes that shape geomorphological landscape, resumed with the term “geodiversity” [2].

Due to its double essence, geodiversity exerts influences on both natural world and human societies, creating not only geohazards and risks but also services, such as those shaping and supporting healthy ecosystems, and offering recreational opportunities. Concrete evidence of the positive interaction

between abiotic environment and human society is shown by the Geosystem Services (GS) [3].

The concept of GS derives from the definition of Ecosystem Services (ES), that are “the goods and benefits provided by the environment to humans” [4]. Whereas the notion of ES is well established in the scientific community, but also among the general public, it is only recently that the idea of GS has been recognised for its fundamental contribution to human welfare.

Even though the word “ecosystem” includes both abiotic and biotic worlds, the framework used in the Millennium Ecosystem Assessment (MEA) focuses mainly on the living features of the environment. Despite the lack of description of abiotic aspects of the ecosystem, various attempt for GS classification have been made by various authors, but two are the most accepted ones: (i) the classification provided by [2], maintaining the four categories proposed by MEA (regulation, support, provision and cultural) and adding a fifth category (knowledge); and (ii) the Common International Classification of Ecosystem Services (CICES) [5], which, in the last version (V5.1), has expanded its abiotic section of ES, showing three categories (provisioning, regulation and maintenance, and cultural).

GS can play a crucial role in bridging the gap between the knowledge on geodiversity and a comprehensive recognition of its contributions to social, economic and ecological benefits that originate from the natural world. This function is particularly relevant within UNESCO Global Geoparks (“UGGs”; areas of international geological interest “managed with a holistic concept of protection, education and sustainable development” [6]), where GS can contribute to conservation, sustainable development and territorial management.

As for the biotic components of the ecosystem, geodiversity elements are considered as “natural resources” essential for a sustainable development of territories through the achievement of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) from the Agenda 2030 [7]. In this framework, an integrated methodology for the analysis of the geodiversity elements and the related services and benefits to the local society have been applied within the piedmont area of the Sesia Val Grande UGGp (SVUGGp). Within this task, both classification typologies have been used in the study area, first singularly, then integrating the results of the two methodologies with the goal of offering a complete representation of goods and benefits offered by the area.

A solid overview of geological resources and GS is intended as a start for further geodiversity actions to support better and comprehensive management of the geopark, thus avoiding the loss of such fundamental geoenvironmental elements.

II. GEO-ENVIRONMENTAL FRAMEWORK

The SVUGGp is one of the twelve Italian UGGps. It is located in the NW Italian Alps, in an area (2202 km²) of particular geological interest. It shows rocks deriving from the mantle and the crust at different depth, including the Sesia Magmatic System [8, 9], a Supervolcano collapsed 280 Ma, the Insubric Line and other palaeogeographical and structural evidence of the Alpine Orogeny [10]. Moreover, lithological and geomorphological diversities are among the reasons of the existence of the SVUGGp.

The SVUGGp’s motto (“where the stone becomes culture”), highlights the profound link of local geological resources and human culture. To further explore this interplay, a target area (72 km²) within the piedmont SVUGGp has been selected for the test of the proposed methodology (Fig. 1).

This area represents a precious insight of a piedmont territory with a rich geodiversity, due to the presence of very different types of rocks (Triassic-Jurassic sedimentary succession of Monte Fenera [11], gneiss of the Serie dei Laghi, Porfidi Quarziferi Complex), glacial, fluvio-glacial and fluvial deposits [12] and different geomorphological landscapes (Fig. 1c).

The area shows perfectly traces of a past “stone culture” [10], as for in the territories of the Monte Fenera Natural Park, with the numerous caverns as Palaeolithic human settlements [13], and the important role of the subsurface as a resource, for both mining activities [14] and wine production purposes, such as in the municipalities of the Boca DOC wine.

III. METHODS

The methodology consists of a first part of literature review of environmental and territorial data, followed by remote sensing analysis and a field survey of the study area, in order to create an information system (by means of QGIS software) and to map the geodiversity at different level of details.

Fig. 1. a) Location of Italian UGGps (orange dots) and SVUGGp (green dot); b) SVUGGp area (red square: study area); c) Geology of the study area (from [12]).

The use of hydrogeological, geomorphological and geological maps, combined with digital elevation models (DEMs), allows the identification of those areas in which benefits and services from the abiotic environment can be potentially found.

Moreover, cultural and socio-economic aspects related to the abiotic environment and the geosphere have been mapped, in order to better individuate the Geosystem Services provided in the area and to integrate them into territorial management plans.

After the collection of the environmental, geological, geomorphological and cultural data, GS have been classified according to [2], followed by a second attempt using the abiotic extension of the CICES method [5]. The two classifications are made comparing the results of the integration of the different maps in the GIS with the lists provided by [2] and [5]. Finally, a combination of the two methods have been performed, in order to implement the knowledge about the study area in terms of resources and services. This step includes an alignment of both frameworks, with the identification of overlapping, and the integration of the two classifications, generating a single thematic map showing the distribution of the integrated Geosystem Services.

IV. RESULT AND DISCUSSION

After the analysis of territorial, cultural and socio-economic data, the main human activities connected with geological and geomorphological contents (“human geoactivities”) in the area have been identified and mapped, in order to enrich the geodiversity values of the territory through the GS provided. The human geoactivities are: (i) two geosites under review within the “Piemonte Geosites Inventory List” project in the context of the Piemonte Regional Law n. 23/2023 [15] (the Monte Fenera sedimentary succession and the Caldera of Sesia Supervolcano in Prato Sesia); (ii) caves; (iii) hiking trails, cycling routes, cultural paths, cliffs for climbing (i.e. sites allowing the exploration of the territory and the appraisal of its geological and cultural heritage); (iv) Boca DOC vineyards (grapes growing on soils derived from rocks of the Sesia Supervolcano, with traces of clay, sandstones and dolomitic rocks, contributing to mineral richness of wine); (v) geocultural sites (such as the Boca Sanctuary, built with brick from local clay, and located on a vulcanite outcrop from the Sesia Supervolcano); (vi) schools (as local places for education on the geosciences); (vii) active mining sites (for the ongoing extraction of clays and kaolin, porphyry and feldspar, or inactive sites (important for the environmental restoration of the territory).

A synthesis map of the main geological and geomorphological elements and human geoactivities is shown in Fig. 2.

Fig. 2. Synthesis map: geological, geomorphological elements and “human geoactivities” within the piedmont area of SVUGGp.

The interpretation of the map supported a first attempt of classification of the Geosystem Services provided by the territory, according to [2] (Fig. 3a). The analysis revealed each feature could show more than one geosystem service provided, for a total of fifteen types, from the five GS categories: Regulation (2), Supporting (3), Provisioning (4), Cultural (4) and Knowledge (2).

The same area has been assessed according to [5] (Fig. 3b). Even if this method allows very detailed description of biotic ES, results of its application seem not very appropriate for the description of GS: among thirty-one CICES classes, only eight have been found in the study area: Provisioning (3), Regulation and Maintenance (1) and Cultural (4), and each feature shows only one type of GS. Moreover, this method shows a stronger focus on natural aspect, rather than on the interaction of people, geosciences concepts and georesources (e.g. schools, geocultural sites). However, a focus on water resources can be identified, with different classes for each use of the resource and distinguishing surface or groundwater ones. Indeed, the supporting and knowledge functions are not included in the [5] method.

Both [2] and [5] classification methods provide useful territorial, cultural and social information. For this reason, a third attempt of classification has been performed, including both categorisations [2] and [5]. The result is a comprehensive, more complete map (Fig. 4), showing areas where the services provided by the geological resources are directly connected with the natural environment and those where this connection is indirect.

Fig. 3. Comparison of maps from the most accepted classification frameworks for ES and GS within the piedmont area of SVUGGp. a) Results by applying Gray’s method [2]; b) Results by applying the CICES method [5].

Fig. 4. ES-GS map of the study area from integration of [2] and [5].

V. CONCLUSIONS

The UGGps are territories rich in geodiversity, hence they have a high potential for offering geosystem services (GS). Even though various attempts for comprehensive classification of ecosystem services have been made [2, 5], these methodologies do not entirely represent the goods and benefits provided by the abiotic environment to human society. The present study illustrated a comparative classification of GS within a piedmont sector in the Sesia Val Grande UGGp, with the aim of highlighting the most important GS for further territorial management plan development. After separate classification of GS by using first [2] then [5] methods, a final integration of the two methodologies has been performed. The reason of this choice is connected to need of including all the environmental aspects assessed in each methodology. In fact, [5] focuses mainly on the good and benefits provided only by the abiotic components of the environment, while [2] propose a more inclusive classification, in which, next to regulation, provision and cultural services, it includes also the supporting services and the knowledge ones, such as places where it is possible to learn about geology and Earth Sciences. The combined use of the two methodologies allowed advanced understanding of the georesources of the piedmont area of the SVUGGp territory, highlighting areas with a predominance of environmental aspects, and other areas where the human have a central role.

This research prepares the ground for new analysis of both non-living and living components of the SVUGGp ecosystems. Comprehensive multiscale assessments will allow to highlight the areas with stronger biodiversity-geodiversity interactions, in order to implement the management policies to preserve the environment. Further application of the methodology will be addressed both to small sites such as the “Bocchie” clay quarry, (Mineraria di Boca S.p.A. company), to emphasise the richness of GS provided by mining sites, and to the whole area of SVUGGp, to implement environmental knowledge on a Geopark territory.

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